

EFFECT OF DIODE LASERS 675NM IN HARDNESS OF DENTAL CERAMIC

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ABSTRACT

This research was study the effect of diode laser in hardness of the material used in the combinations of teeth (ceramics). Hardness was measured for samples divided into two groups, each group contain ingtentest sample, before and after it irradiated with the diode laser 675nm, 30mW, for a period of (2 and 10) minutes for the first group and for the second one respectively .

The results showed that a significant increase in the hardness of ceramic material for irradiated samples compared to non-irradiated samples, where found that the highest percentage of hardness was (41.6%) obtained up on irradiation with a laser of 675nm, 30mW for duration two minutes.

Key Words: Dental Ceramic, Laser Irradiation and Hardness

INTRODUCTION

Now a day's diode lasers are used in many applications, including spectroscopy, communication, industry, holography and also in medical (Abdelrahman et al., 2013 and Otieno, 1992). Dental Ceramics or porcelain is popular due to the demand for aesthetics and durability of restoration. Dental ceramics consist of mainly glass, porcelain or highly crystalline of structure, the physical or mechanical properties of ceramic are much closer to enamel than those of acrylic resins and method, ceramic also have a coefficient of thermal expansion very close to that of teeth (Garg and Garg, 2010).

Dental ceramics are materials that are part of systems designed with the purpose of producing dental prostheses that in turn, are used to replace missing or damaged dental structures. In dental science, ceramics are referred to as nonmetallic materials made by man through the heating of raw minerals at high temperatures, inorganic structures primarily containing compounds of oxygen with one or more metallic or semi-metallic elements. They are usually sodium, potassium, Calcium, magnesium, aluminum, silicon, phosphorus, zirconium and titanium (Lakshmanan, 2012). Dental are used for variety of dental restoration, these include the fabrication of denture teeth, indirect restorative materials such as single crowns, fixed partial dentures, more recently the use of ceramic has been expanded to include inlays and onlays in posterior teeth, implants (Touati et al., 1999).

There are two interrelated properties that often are quoted regarding ceramics intended for structural purposes: Strength, and fracture toughness. Classification of ceramics in dentistry is apparently an impossible task due to vast improvements made in the compositions; Dental ceramics may be classified according to several parameters, such as their use, microstructure (i.e., amount and type of crystalline phase and glass composition), manufacturing temperature, ceramic system, composition, and processing technique. Lasers interactions with tissue are complicated and no single parameter alone will determine how the laser affects the tissue. Dental hard tissue applications include ablation of carious lesions, cavity preparation for restoration, caries detection, endodontic surgery and the potential for caries preventive therapy. The parameters of prime concern in understanding desirable or undesirable tissue effects are wavelength, pulse duration, absorption properties, scattering, energy, flounce (energy/surface area), power density, repetition rate, number of pulses, pulse duration and pulse shape. A range of laser parameters has been found with which dental enamel can be treated to make it resistant to subsequent dissolution by acid during dental caries. Our studies have demonstrated that treatment of enamel by specific pulsed carbon dioxide laser irradiation can markedly inhibit subsequent caries progression. During irradiation, heat causes carbonate loss from the carbonated hydroxyapatite mineral, converting it into a low solubility hydroxyapatite-like calcium phosphate (Donald J Colluzzi, DDS. FACD).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Equipment

In this study the diode laser of the wavelength 675nm, output power 30mW, power density 0.24 W/cm², spot size 0.125 cm², pulsing repetition rate 146 Hz, class 3B laser product non ionization radiation, Omega Laser System Company; England was used to irradiate the dental ceramic (ORA). Dental ceramic firing furnace used in this study

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is type Centurion Q50 Vacuum Porcelain Furnace from ivoclar vivadent technical -ivoclar Inc company, United State and Canada. The Q50 offers the quality expected from the Centurion line of vacuum porcelain furnaces at an affordable price. With operator friendly controls figure (1) shows the photo of this furnace.

Figure 1: Centurion Q50 Vacuum Porcelain Furnace

The hardness tester used in this study is type (TH 160), supplied from Digiwork Instruments Company, Orantio Canada (Horst et al., 2006). UVmini-1240 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer was used in this study to measured absorption spectrum of dental ceramic materials. UVmini-1240 features a variety of standard data acquisition modes, including spectral scanning over the wavelength range of (190 - 1100) nm.

Materials

Dental ceramic materials used in this study are powder opaque B₁, and dentine B₁ from Ceramco 3. and also used anickel chromium metal.

Preparation of Ceramic Specimens

First, anickel chromium as base metal alloy used to fabricate 20 specimens for ceramic material, measuring 10 mm in diameter and 4 mm in thickness of the metal plus allayer 1.7 mm thickness of the ceramic material. Then, Ceramic powder (dentin and opaque powder) was mixed with distilled water to form slurry and then the mixed slurry was loaded into nickel chromium mold as a layer. Before that, the specimens were placed on a firing tray (Centurion Q50 Vacuum Porcelain Furnace) they were dried and sintered in a vacuum furnace according to manufacturer's specification at temperature of 850°C.

The prepared 20 specimens were divided as follows

Twenty specimens of conventional dental ceramic were prepared to study in this work; Figure (2) shows photographs of them.

Figure 2: Photographs of the specimens

Procedure and Methods

1. The dental ceramic layer was added into twenty specimens of nickel chromium base metal alloy.
2. The dental ceramic layer was subjected to the test of strength was measure the hardness for each specimen before the laser irradiation (pre-test), by using birnell hardness test.
3. The laser safety Goggles (protective eyewear) were used.

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4. Twenty specimens were divided into two groups, ten in each according to irradiated time. The first group irradiated with diode laser 675nm at power 30mW for two minutes, while the second group irradiated for ten minutes.

5. The hardness test (post-test) of all specimens, has been measured the same condition of the first one,

6. The comparison of the (post-test) with the (pre-test) have been done.

Spectroscopic Study

The combination teeth material (dental ceramic) was studied spectroscopic by using UVmini-1240 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer, to observe the absorption spectrum of the dental ceramics at any range of wavelength. The results were listed in tables and analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Studies (SPSS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result obtained from the experiments will be listed in tables and figures and then discussed the results. The results divided into two parts according to the effect of the two wavelength of diode laser 675 nm that used in experiment.

Results of Irradiation with Diode Laser 675 nm/30 mW

The results of the hardness test of the combination teeth material (ceramic) before and after irradiation by diode laser 675 nm were listed in the tables, was measured change for harness, and it is percentage after irradiation. The results of irradiation with diode laser at wavelength 675 nm, and power 30 mW, in two different duration two and ten minutes were listed in table (1) and table (2) respectively.

Table 1: Measurement of hardness of dental ceramic specimens irradiated by diode laser 675 nm and power 30 mW for time 2 minutes

Specimen Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Means
(pre-test) (HB)	39	55	31	42	35	33	37	31	35	39	37.7
(post-test) (HB)	49	65	39	60	39	38	40	37	39	45	45.1
Hardness change (HB)	10	10	8	8	4	5	3	6	4	6	7.4
Change %	25.64	18.18	25.81	42.86	11.43	15.1	8.11	19.3	11.4	15.3	19.63

Figure 3 shows plot of increasing of hardness for ten specimens without and after irradiation with 675 nm and energy output power 30 mW, at irradiation time two minutes.

Figure 3: Measurement of hardness of dental ceramic specimens before and after irradiated by diode laser 675 nm/30mW for two minutes

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Table 2: Measurement of hardness of dental ceramic specimens irradiated by diode laser 675 nm and power 30 mW for time 10 minutes

Specimens Number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Means
(pre-test) (HB)	53	35	38	45	31	37	35	32	41	38	38.5
(post-test) (HB)	67	49	55	53	48	51	53	56	59	54	54.5
Hardness change (HB)	14	14	17	8	17	14	18	24	18	16	16
Change %	26.4	40.0	44.7	17.8	54.8	37.8	51.4	75.0	43.9	42.1	41.6

Figure 4 shows plot of increasing of hardness for ten specimens without and after irradiation with 675 nm and energy output power 30 mW, at irradiation time ten minutes.

Figure 4: Measurement of hardness of dental ceramic specimens before and after irradiated by diode laser 675 nm/30mW for ten minutes

The comparison of average change of hardness at irradiation time two and ten minute, at constant power 30 mW , Figure (5) shows decrease in hardness with increasing of irradiation time.

Figure 5: comparison of the hardness measurement for irradiation time two and ten minute and power 30 mW

The hardness average change and the percentage of hardness decrease for irradiation time 2 to 10 min, the different between the values of them as shown in fig. 6.

Figure 6: Measurement of hardness average change and percentage of dental ceramic for irradiation time two and ten minutes

Discussion of Results

At duration two minutes the observed measurements that higher increasing of the hardness percentage was (41.6%) comparison of duration ten minutes it was (19.63%), consequently the hardness average change and hardness percentage were decrease gradually with increasing duration .So the increase in duration for longer periods does not have a significant in the hardness ratio. Figure 6 shows clearly the inverse relationship between duration and the hardness of dental ceramic at irradiation with diode laser 675 nm, 30 mW.

CONCLUSION

The obtained results one can find that; Irradiation with diode laser at shorter wavelength (675 nm) increases the hardness of dental ceramic better than dental ceramic without irradiation. Diode laser 675 nm/30 mW showed a promising effect on the hardness of dental ceramic.

REFERENCES

- Abdelrahman A, Abdelrahman M & Elbadawy M (2013).** Possibility of using the beet dyes as a laser gain medium. *Natural Science*, 5(11) 1183-1188.
- Donald J. Colluzzi, DDS & FACD.** The dentistry Network. Dentistry iQ.
- Garg N & Garg A (2010).** Text Book of Operative Dentistry. Jaypee Brothers, Medical Publishers.
- Horst C, Tetsuya S & Smith L (2006).** Springer Hand book of material measurement method. Springer, London New York.
- Lakshmanan A (2012).** Sintering of Ceramics New Emerging Techniques. InTech Publisher.
- Otieno AV (1992).** The splendour of light. Nairobi University press 1.
- ORA-laser jet, oralia medical GmbH.** Schneckenburgstraße 11. Available at: www.oralia.com/en/downloads/oralaserjet.pdf
- Touati B, Miara P & Nathanson D (1999).** Esthetic dentistry and ceramic resoration, Martin Dunitz London.